

Can Perfume Allergy Cause Glycosuria?

Mah Rukh*, Aqsa Naeem, Abida Bibi, Syed Bilal Hussain & Muhammad Imran Qadir

Institute of Molecular Biology & Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.
Corresponding Author (Mah Rukh) - mahrukhmahboob21@gmail.com*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46382/MJBAS.2023.7103>

Copyright: © 2023 Mah Rukh et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Article Received: 11 December 2022

Article Accepted: 25 January 2023

Article Published: 15 February 2023

ABSTRACT

The main aim of this research is to correlate relation between ornament allergy and glycosuria. Glycosuria is a process in which glucose is removed from urine. The value of glucose in blood must be less than 7 mmol/L. Glycosuria is caused by diabetes, high sugar diet, emotion and liver cirrhosis. Some people are sensitive to some fragrances or ornaments when they come in contact with these ornaments, they show marks of allergy like disease in respiratory track, fever, rashes and headache. The best treatment is to avoid such ornaments having unpleasant sharp smell which cause rashes. 17% males have glucose in urine and show perfume allergy while 1.25% females have glucose in urine and have perfume allergy.

Keywords: Glycosuria; Perfume allergy; Urine; Liver cirrhosis.

Introduction

Glycosuria is a process in which glucose is removed from urine. Normally there is no glucose in urine because kidney is able to absorb all salt and glucose from blood. In children's and pregnant women's, the value of glucose in blood must be less than 7 mmol/L. If this value increases it causes diabetes type 1. The main symptoms of urine glucose are hunger, fatigue, infection in urinary track, weight loss and abdominal pain. Glycosuria is caused by diabetes, high sugar diet, emotion and liver cirrhosis. The glucose level in urine can be easily checked by urine test. Monitor your diet and maintain your glucose level prevent us from all these kinds of problems.

Some people are sensitive to some fragrances or ornaments when they come in contact with these ornaments, they show marks of allergy like disease in respiratory track, fever, rashes and headache. Every chemical has different sign of allergy. It can be controlled easily at initial stage but in serious condition it even causes death due to severe infection in respiratory track. "Headache, breath difficulty, wheezing, chest tightening, asthma and stuffy nose" are the most common symptoms. In early 2-3 weeks it can be cured. The best treatment is to avoid such ornaments and products which cause rashes and having unpleasant sharp smell.

Materials and Methods

100 participants of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan involved in this study.

We tested glucose in urine-by-urine sample. A small chip called dipstick was used to measure the level of glucose in urine. This stick changes its color according to the concentration of urine glucose.

This study coordinates perfume allergy with glycosuria.

Results and Discussions

Total 17% males have urine glucose and show perfume allergy. 75% males have no urine glucose but show perfume allergy. 0% males have urine glucose and they don't have perfume allergy. 8% males have no urine

glucose and don't shows perfume allergy. 1.25% females have urine glucose and show perfume allergy. 87% females have no urine glucose but show perfume allergy. 1.25% females have urine glucose but show no perfume allergy. 10.5% females have no urine glucose and don't show perfume allergy as well.

Questionnaire based studies is very important as it helps to generate reliable results. It allows the participation of people from different areas and ethnicity thus, providing more reliable results.

Table 1. Co-ordination of perfume allergy with glycosuria

Gender	Perfume Allergy		Don't have perfume allergy	
	Glucose in urine	No glucose in urine	Glucose in urine	No glucose in urine
Male	17%	75%	0%	8%
Female	1.25%	87%	1.25%	10.5%

Conclusion

17% males have glucose in urine and show perfume allergy while 1.25% females have glucose in urine and have perfume allergy. This study thus concludes that perfume allergic people can have normal levels of glucose in urine.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

References

- [1] Ostrom L. (2015). *Perfume: a century of scents*, Random House.
- [2] Kumar M., Devi A., Sharma M., Kaur P., Mandal U.K. (2021). Review on perfume and present status of its associated allergens. *J. Cosmet. Dermatol.*, 20: 391–399. doi: 10.1111/jocd.13507.
- [3] Qadir MI, Naeem A. (2019). Blood Group Effects On Perfume Allergy. *World J Adv Med Pharm Res*, 2(1): Pages 31–33.
- [4] Cha J, Shin CW, Son WG. (2021). Transient postoperative glycosuria after isoflurane exposure in two dogs. *J Small Anim Pract.*, 62(11): 102–1025. doi: 10.1111/jsap.13314.
- [5] Jagła M, Szymońska I, Starzec K, Kwinta P. (2018). Preterm Glycosuria - New Data from a Continuous Glucose Monitoring System. *Neonatology*, 114(1): 87–92. doi: 10.1159/000487846.